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Description:

This document describes the first version of the data management plan of the NEMESIS project, to be submitted as deliverable D7.3 in WP7.

It is published at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20995717>.

1 Introduction

NEMESIS is an international research project that aims to uncover new physics beyond the Standard Model by combining two powerful approaches in particle physics: the high-intensity frontier of muons and the high-precision frontier of ultracold neutrons and polarized muons.

NEMESIS focuses on precision measurements and rare processes, where even the smallest deviation from theory could reveal entirely new physical laws. To reach this ambitious goal, the project develops cutting-edge technologies, including high-intensity particle beams, state-of-the-art detectors, innovative data acquisition systems, and advanced analysis tools. The collaboration unites leading researchers from Europe, Switzerland, and the United States, working across three major international laboratories: Fermilab (FNAL) and Brookhaven National Laboratory (BNL) in the USA, and the Paul Scherrer Institute (PSI) in Switzerland.

During the duration of the NEMESIS project (from 1.1.2026 to 31.12.2029), this first version of the Data Management Plan will be regularly evaluated and eventually adjusted to suit the needs of the NEMESIS researchers.

2 Data Management Plan

The Horizon Europe Model Grant Agreement requires that a data management plan ('DMP') is established and regularly updated.

This document, which is based on the template provided by the European Commission for Horizon Europe beneficiaries, serves as a "code of conduct" document about how we want to manage the research data and meta data created by the NEMESIS project.

2.1 Data Coordinator

The Data Coordinator for the NEMESIS Data Management is

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Stefan Müller is designated as a contact person for data management issues and will forward any questions to the Management Board of NEMESIS, which will oversee the

data management of the different project partners.

2.2 Data Summary

In the NEMESIS project, several types of research data are currently dealt with:

- *Collaboration data:* This is data produced by NEMESIS researchers within the framework of larger collaborations
- *Test beam data:* These datasets are collected by NEMESIS researchers using test beams at dedicated test beam facilities in Europe or US
- *Simulation data:* These are datasets created by NEMESIS researchers by doing studies with radiation transport and interaction program packages

Should the need arise during the NEMESIS project to introduce further types of research data, this Data Management Plan will be accordingly adjusted.

2.2.1 Datasets - re-use and formats

Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use them for?

In general, no existing data will be re-used by the NEMESIS project.

For *simulation data*, the main purpose of the simulations is to study detector design under varying conditions, do shielding assessments and develop and optimize neutron moderator systems for the production of cold-neutron beams. These simulations need to be specifically designed to the corresponding case.

Data taken in *test beams* is used to qualify a piece of equipment (e.g. a detector) for a specific task under well-defined conditions. These test beams usually serve as preparations for larger experiments. Again these test beam experiments address very specific needs, which in general do not allow to re-use existing data sets.

The data sets produced in the framework of large *collaborations* are unique data sets explicitly created to address very specific scientific questions. They will supersede existing data sets and results. To some extent, results from test beam data may be used here for calibration purposes or cross checks.

State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded

Simulation data: Many work packages in the NEMESIS project include simulation studies using radiation transport programs. The main purpose of the simulations is to study detector design under varying conditions or do shielding assessments. Simulation studies are always very specific to the case under study, and often many iterations are needed to

get the desired outcome of the simulation calculation. Therefore it is usually not feasible to re-use existing simulation data.

Test beam data: In general, test beam data is used to characterize a certain behavior or performance of equipment under well defined conditions, such that the equipment can be used for future experimental activities. To that extend, the large collaborations in which NEMESIS researchers are engaged may use the outcome of test beam experiments for their work.

Collaboration data: New data sets will be produced in the framework of larger collaborations during the NEMESIS project duration to answer dedicated scientific questions. The experiments built and used by these collaborations are unique one-of-a-kind experiments. As mentioned above, results from test beam data may be used here for calibration purposes or cross checks.

What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?

Simulation data: Simulation data sets are produced using dedicated radiation transport programs like GEANT4, FLUKA, PHITS or MCNP. In addition to conventional simulation outputs, moderator studies may generate processed low-temperature neutron scattering libraries obtained from evaluated nuclear data using NJOY, as well as NCrystal material descriptions for crystalline materials where appropriate.

The resulting datasets may include neutron spectra, moderator response functions, flux distributions, detector response functions, energy-deposition maps and shielding quantities. The simulation workflow also produces input decks, processed cross-section libraries, ACE files, NCrystal configuration files, processing scripts and meta-data required to ensure reproducibility.

Output data are typically stored in ROOT, binary Fortran, HDF5, CSV or ASCII formats. These data sets are produced (and stored) at a certain point in time, but often several iterations are needed to obtain the desired outcome.

Test beam data: Test beam data is usually taken during specific test beam periods, which can last from few days to few weeks.

The format can vary, and can be simple tabular sheets, csv-formatted data or also ROOT-files.

Collaboration data: These data will be collected using dedicated DAQ systems tailored explicitly to the needs of the corresponding experiment. The data format is usually defined by the collaboration and does not necessarily follow a common standardized structure. The data will be produced over longer time period (from several months to years).

What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?

For *simulation data*, the main purpose of the simulations is to study detector design under varying conditions or do shielding assessments.

The data taken in *test beams* is used to qualify a piece of equipment (e.g. a detector) for a specific task under well-defined conditions. These test beams usually serve as preparations for larger experiments.

The data sets of *collaboration* will be used by the respective collaborations to address specific scientific questions laid out in the corresponding Work Packages of the NEMESIS project.

What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?

Collaboration data: The datasets which involve large collaborations in WP1 and WP2 can easily be several PB.

Test beam data: A test beam dataset can accumulate from a hundred GB to several TB, and test beam datasets will be either stored at the test beam facility and/or at the IT infrastructure of a NEMESIS project partner

Simulation data: Simulation campaigns can reach from several tens of GB to several tens of TB, depending how much information one wants to keep (histogrammed data vs. list-mode-data).

What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?

Simulation data: These data sets are produced by NEMESIS researchers according to their needs, and stored on location. To fulfill the FAIR criteria, the simulation meta data like input files or code packages and program versions used to produce the data sets can be published in a data repository. For simulations involving cryogenic moderators, the provenance of the nuclear data and material models will also be documented. This includes the original evaluated nuclear data (e.g. ENDF evaluations distributed through NNDC or equivalent libraries), NJOY processing input decks, generated ACE libraries, NCrystal material description files, simulation input decks, code versions and processing scripts.

Test beam data: The test beam data will be created on site at the test beam facility. Depending on the facility's data policy and the needs of the researchers, data will be stored at the test beam facility or at the researcher's institution. Post-processing steps need to be properly documented and stored by the researchers analyzing the data.

Collaboration data: The provenance of the data will be handled and properly documented by the corresponding collaborations.

To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?

In general, the data produced by the NEMESIS project might be useful for other scientists who work in the same or similar field.

2.3 FAIR data

2.3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Will the data be identified by a persistent identifier?

The data sets will be uploaded to a data repository (e.g. ZENODO or one of the institutional repositories listed at the end of this document) and will therefore have a DOI which can be cited and allows to find and access the data.

Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed?

The data sets published on a data repository will be described using the DataCite metadata scheme.

For the large-scale experiments used by the collaborations in which NEMESIS researchers are involved, all metadata for collaboration data is collected automatically through the corresponding DAQ systems, which are specially designed for the experiments. This is also true for simulation campaigns carried out within these collaborations.

Whether metadata are collected automatically for *test beam* data sets varies and depends on the test beam facility as well as the individual data taking approach used for the test beam experiments. While some test beam experiments may require a manual collection of meta data, others may employ a dedicated DAQ system which allows for automatic collection of metadata.

For smaller simulation campaigns performed by individual NEMESIS researchers, the metadata usually needs to be collected manually.

Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?

All data sets uploaded to a dedicated data repository will have keywords assigned. Especially the Durham HEPData project provides domain-specific keywords for reaction data in high-energy- and particle physics. For *simulation data*, we will provide adequate keywords to describe the simulation environment and procedures.

Will metadata be offered in such a way that they can be harvested and indexed?

For *simulation* and *test beam* data sets, the meta data shall be published on data repositories which allow harvesting through the OAI-PMH protocol. This is fulfilled for the institutional repositories listed at the end of this document, as well as the CERN-hosted ZENODO data repository.

For *collaboration data*, upload on a data repository will also be envisioned, but this depends on the data policies of the collaborations which own the data.

2.3.2 Making data accessible

Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?

Some of NEMESIS partner institutions provide their own data repositories to which data sets may be uploaded. While these repositories may restrict data uploads to members of the corresponding institution, the CERN-hosted ZENODO platform (<https://zenodo.org/>) is an alternative which allows data uploads up to 50 GB by everyone. All these repositories allow harvesting through the OAI-PMH protocol.

All these repositories are trusted because they fulfill the following criteria:

- Machine-actionable and standardised metadata are used
- The repository meets the basic expectations of a research data repository: easy and free access while observing legal and ethical barriers, detailed metadata, protection against unauthorized access
- The repository can provide persistent identifiers, e.g. a DOI
- The repository is internationally acknowledged for the a specific discipline/domain
- The repository is managed by a trustworthy institution
- The repository's policy is available online

Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?

The data will be uploaded via a standard procedure and no special arrangements are required.

Does the repository ensure that the data are assigned an identifier?

Yes, the repositories will assign a DOI to the uploaded data.

Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?

Yes, the repositories will resolve the DOI to a digital object.

Will all data be made openly available?

For *collaboration data sets*, the policies of the collaborations which own the data sets apply. While NEMESIS researchers will work towards making also these data sets FAIR and openly available, at the moment it is not foreseen to make *collaboration data sets* fully openly available.

Simulation and *test beam* data sets can be made openly available, or at least being uploaded to a repository with individual approval for external users.

If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions.

As mentioned above, the policies of the collaborations which own the data sets apply for *collaboration data sets*, and may hinder a fully open publication of the data sets.

If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.

In general, the data sets should not be made public before the corresponding results are published in a peer-reviewed journal or a thesis based on these data sets is finalized.

Under which terms of use or license will the dataset be published or shared?

It is planned to share or publish data sets under a Creative Commons Attribution (CC-BY) licence.

If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?

For *simulation data*, in principle, there are no restrictions to re-use these data sets, but since only the simulation meta data will be published (which in principle allow to recreate the data set), the user needs to be licensed for the radiation transport programs needed to produce the data sets.

For *test beam data* sets, other than embargo periods to allow for finalizing journal publications or PhD theses, there are in principle no restrictions to re-use the test beam data sets after publication.

For *collaboration data*, the data policies of the collaborations apply, which may or may not foresee the publication or re-use of the data sets.

How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?

In case data are still only available in a restricted way, the repositories will forward the request to the uploader of the data, who will properly identify the requester if needed before allowing the use of the data.

Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?

No, no dedicated data access committee is needed, since in general no personal or sensitive information is contained in the data.

Will metadata be made openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why.

For *simulation data* and *test beam* data metadata for data which accompanies a journal publication will be made available under an open license.

For *collaboration data* sets, the data policies of the collaborations apply, which may not foresee the publication of the metadata.

Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?

Dataset Simulation data: The metadata in this case will make it possible for the user to reproduce the simulation calculations. Therefore data access is not required.

Dataset Test beam data: Access to the data and metadata will be through a data repository. If needed, software required to process the data will be additionally published.

Dataset Collaboration data: The data policies of the collaborations apply, which may restrict access to collaboration members only.

How long will the data remain available and findable?

The data should remain available and findable for at least 10 years.

Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data are no longer available?

This depends on the data repository. In principle, many of the aforementioned repositories treat data and metadata in the same identical way, so if the data disappears, so does the metadata.

Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data be included?

Will it be possible to include the relevant software (*e.g.* in open source code)?

In case specific software is needed to access or read the data, this will be documented in the corresponding README-file which will accompany the data upload in the data repository. Should these software be developed by NEMESIS researchers, it will be also made available under an open source licence on one of the data repositories mentioned above.

2.3.3 Making data interoperable

What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines?

Collaboration data: The data produced within the framework of a larger collaboration will be made available to members of the collaboration and therefore will be produced in a standardized format defined by the collaboration. Also the required software tools will be made available within the collaborations. Data published in journal articles will be provided in a standardized form (e.g. ASCII files) to allow for easy re-use.

Test beam data: In the particle physics community, data are often stored in the ROOT format. In case other formats are used in the data taking, they will be converted to ROOT files or even ASCII files using Open Source tools.

Simulation data: Since the simulation programs used are widely used in the community, reproducing the simulation results should be straight forward, provided experience with the corresponding program is given.

Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?

As a basic metadata scheme, <http://schema.datacite.org/> may be used, which is supported for example by HZDR's RODARE and the ZENODO data repositories. The Durham HEPData project provides more detailed metadata information, but mainly focuses on reaction cross sections in High Energy Physics. For data in journal publications, a meta data catalogue like SCICAT (<https://www.scicatproject.org/>) can be used, which is offered for example at HZDR (<https://scicat.hzdr.de> or PSI (<https://doi.psi.ch/>)).

In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies?

Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining or extending them?

It is currently not foreseen within the scope of the NEMESIS project to provide or create mappings between ontologies.

Will your data include qualified references to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?

If needed, the data will include qualified references to other data sets when uploaded to a data repository.

2.3.4 Increase data re-use

How will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use

(e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?

The documentation will be in general included in the repository upload, in the form of:

- Information on methodology used for data generation (creation or re-use) and transformation
- Description of variables used and respective units of measurement
- Version information
- Data formats

Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible?

For *collaboration data sets*, the policies of the collaborations which own the data sets apply. While NEMESIS researchers will work towards making also these data sets FAIR, at the moment it is not foreseen to make *collaboration data sets* fully openly and freely available.

Simulation and *test beam* data sets can be made freely available at no charge.

Will your data be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?

Yes, the data will be licensed with a Creative Commons Attribution (CC-BY) or similar when uploaded to a repository.

Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

The data which will be uploaded to a data repository will be available for re-use.

Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?

Yes, the provenance of the data will be documented using appropriate standards.

Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.

The data will in general be checked on completeness and calibration procedures.

Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security and ethical aspects.

We will address these aspects in the following section.

2.4 Other research outputs

In addition to the management of data, beneficiaries should also consider and plan for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout their projects.

The project will also produce research output in the form of software products (macros, scripts, tools, programs,...).

Beneficiaries should consider which of the questions pertaining to FAIR data above can apply to the management of other research outputs, and should strive to provide sufficient detail on how their research outputs will be managed and shared, or made available for re-use, in line with the FAIR principles.

Software tools produced within the NEMESIS project will be treated in the same way as data or metadata produced in the project (e.g. publication on ZENODO or one of the institutional repositories listed at the end of this document).

2.5 Allocation of resources

What will the costs be for making data or other research outputs FAIR in your project

It is assumed that the NEMESIS partner institutions will cover the funds to make FAIR data, so no funds from the NEMESIS project are needed.

How will these be covered?

Since data FAIRness is in the interest of all involved partner institutions, the institutions will support the NEMESIS project by contributing the general resources to make data FAIR (archiving infrastructure, repository costs, person months).

Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Stefan E. Müller from HZDR has been nominated as the project's data coordinator.

How will long term preservation be ensured? Discuss the necessary resources to accomplish this

A data storage of at least 10 years (preferably longer) should be provided by the participating institutions as part of good scientific practice. In case data is published on a data repository, the repository will take care of the storage.

Criteria for preservation:

In first place, data which is relevant in the context of a journal publication should be archived. In general, if data or metadata needs to be shared (within the NEMESIS project or with external researchers), an upload to a data repository should be considered (in this case, the data will be archived by the repository).

Motivation for long-term preservation:

Collaboration data: All the experimental collaborations in WP1 and WP2 are designing and running unique one-of-a-kind experiments pushing the precision in their respective domains. Therefore it is mandatory to preserve the data for a long period in order to be able to revisit the data in case controversial or new results are found in the future.

Test beam data: The test beam data will lay the foundation for future developments e.g. in detector development. Therefore it is important that these data are preserved.

Simulation data: In fact there is no urgent need to preserve the simulation data itself, as in principle it can be reproduced given the simulation procedures and input files. However, for some very large-scale simulation campaigns, it may be more efficient to store the data than to re-run the procedure. This is sometimes the case when simulations are done in the framework of a large collaboration. In that case, collaboration guidelines on data management describe which simulation datasets are to be stored long-term together with the experimental data.

2.6 Data security

What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?

Collaboration data: The data taken by the experimental collaborations will be reliably stored and archived at the Computing Divisions of the hosting institutes (e.g. FNAL, PSI). Tools like KERBEROS authentication and dedicated Two-Factor authentication prevent the access of unauthorized people to the data.

Test beam data: The data is in general not security critical (unless patent or copyright restrictions by involved industrial partners apply, in this case, they will take care of securely storing the data). Nevertheless, safe long-term data storage is important. Data is digital only. Raw data will be backed up and archived at the local institutions where the data is produced using existing procedures. If data needs to be distributed, this will ideally be done using data repositories.

Simulation data: The simulation procedures and input files as well as the simulation data will be stored primarily on a server at one of the project partner's IT departments, with a corresponding backup- and archiving infrastructure and regulations for data management. The simulation procedures and input files which are relevant for reproducing the results in a published journal article should be uploaded to a reliable data repository like the CERN-hosted ZENODO or one of the institutional data repositories listed at the end of this document.

Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long-term preservation and curation?

The chosen repositories are trustworthy, as described above.

2.7 Ethics

Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?

There are no ethical or legal aspects that will impact the sharing of NEMESIS datasets.

Will informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

The "informed consent" is not obtained, since in general the data does not deal with personal data.

2.8 Other issues

Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones? (Please list and briefly

describe them.)

There already exist dedicated regulations and policies of the involved partner institutions:

Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique

- CNRS Research Data Plan
- CNRS operates a Research Data repository at <https://entrepot.recherche.data.gouv.fr/>

FNAL:

- Data Management Plan of the Mu2e experiment at Fermilab: <https://publicdocs.fnal.gov/cgi-bin/ShowDocument?docid=515>

Heidelberg University:

- Heidelberg University Research Data Policy
- Heidelberg University operates the heiDATA Institutional Repository for Research Data at <https://heidata.uni-heidelberg.de/>

Helmholtz-Zentrum Dresden-Rossendorf:

- HZDR's data policy: <https://www.hzdr.de/db/Cms?p0id=57725>
- HZDR supports its members and visiting scientists by operating the "Rossendorf Data Repository" RODARE at <https://rodare.hzdr.de/>. It also recently implemented a SciCat repository at <https://scicat.hzdr.de>

Jagiellonian University Kraków:

- Open Access Policy to scholarly publications and research data of the Jagiellonian University: <https://pod.uj.edu.pl/polityka-otwartosci-uj>
- the Jagiellonian University Kraków is a member of RODBUK, the Cracow Open Research Data Repository: <https://home.rodbuk.pl>

University of Liverpool

- University of Liverpool Research Data Management Policy
- University of Liverpool's Research Data Catalogue <https://datacat.liverpool.ac.uk/>

University College London

- The UCL Research Data Policy has been published at <https://doi.org/10.5522/04/25579800>
- UCL operates a Research Data Repository at <https://rdr.ucl.ac.uk/>

Johannes Gutenberg-Universität Mainz

- JGU Guidelines for research data management(in german)
- JGU operates a Open Science Repository at <https://openscience.ub.uni-mainz.de>

University of Padova

- University of Padova Research Data Policy
- The University of Padova operates a Research Data Archive at <https://researchdata.cab.unipd.it/>

PSI:

- PSI data policy for external users: <https://www.psi.ch/en/media/74588/download?attachment>
- Mu3e Data Preservation and Access Policy at <https://www.psi.ch/en/media/95978/download?attachment>
- PSI operates a Public Data Repository at <https://doi.psi.ch/>

Rutherford Appleton Laboratory

- Data Policy of the ISIS neutron and muon source: <https://www.isis.stfc.ac.uk/Pages/Data-Policy.aspx>
- RAL hosts the ISIS Neutron and Muon Source Data Repository at <https://data.isis.stfc.ac.uk/datagateway>

Additional project-internal regulations are still to be established, and will be properly documented in the Data Management Plan.